

TERglove: a modular low-cost IMU-based Data Glove

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Abstract—For humans, the hands represent the most important medium of interaction with the environment. In fact, their sophisticated kinematic structure and perception abilities allow to hold objects, perform gestures and perceive contact forces. The development of tools capable of detecting this information has become increasingly important in recent years given the implications in various fields ranging from medicine to robotics.

Index Terms—Data Glove, Hand Tracking, Motion Analysis, Wearable Sensors.

I. INTRODUCTION

The progress of our civilisation has been greatly aided by the structure [1] of the human hand, which allows for adequate dexterity to grasp, move, and operate objects. This characteristic is also essential to analyze the majority of our daily activities involving tools and influences many different research fields, e.g., surgery, rehabilitation [2], gesture recognition [3], robotics [4] and human-machine interaction [5].

When humans use their hands to interact with objects, they make use of their sensorial perception abilities to regulate the position of the fingers and the magnitude of the forces to be exerted. Proprioception and touch are two senses that we can use to distinguish the information that our hand is able to gather. The former allows us to track how our limbs are positioned in space, while the latter identifies and quantifies contact forces. Different technological approaches are available to measure these information and the researchers can decide to consider both the aspects or to focus on a single one. Wearable sensors and vision-based techniques [6] are the two main available for the proprioception sense. On the other hand, contact forces are mainly obtained using wearable pressure sensors, with the exception of few estimation solutions based on cameras [7].

Data gloves are sensorized glove-shaped devices specifically designed to simulate the human perception. Depending on the type and number of sensors, they can track the movement of the fingers or the contact forces. In the first case, the main types of sensors are the flex sensors, the inertial measurement units (IMU) and the magnetic trackers, while for the second

Fig. 1. The picture shows the experimental setup with the 11-IMUs configuration, which is connected to the AR10 hand by means of 3D printed supports.

task pressure sensors are the most common choice and they can be integrated in synergy with vibrating motors or air chambers to provide a feedback to the user.

In this work we present a low-cost, modular architecture to develop an IMU-based data glove and the experimental procedure we used to test its performance.

II. GLOVE ARCHITECTURE

The design of our glove is focused on a modular architecture which can support a variable number of IMUs depending on the task and the fingers that the user needs to track.

The glove is equipped with a Lithium-Polymer battery to be independent of any other external components and the choice for a modular architecture facilitates the substitution of the sensors for maintainance.

The main module (ESP32-WROOM-32) consists of a micro-controller unit (MCU), a wireless interface, the battery and one IMU and can work on its own but also contains the interface to connect the other modules.

The additional modules consist of 9-axis MPU9250 IMUs with two connectors each, which can be easily daisy-chained and connected to the core module.

The communication relies on the I2C standard because it can support multiple devices on the same bus without the need for additional selection lines. For the physical interface we chose the Flexible Flat Cable (FFC) connectors and cables which are flexible enough to avoid obstructions during the usage.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

We designed the experimental setup to evaluate the performances of the glove during prolonged usage. The core module and 10 additional IMUs were used to carry out the experiments, resulting in two sensors for each finger and one for the back of the hand.

The glove's battery duration and the frequency at which it can transmit sensor data were the goal of the first test that was performed leaving the glove on a static position over a flat surface until the battery ran out. With the 11 sensors connected, the results show that the mean duration of the battery is 61 ± 7.3 minutes and the frequency can reach 25 Hz.

Knowing the expected battery duration, we designed a second set of experiments to assess the performance of the hardware during human-like motion using a robotic system composed of a Baxter manipulator by ReThink Robotics¹ and an Active8 AR10² antropomorphic hand with 2 degrees of freedom for each finger. As shown in Figure 1 the AR10 hand served as the end-effector for Baxter's arm and the glove was linked to it using custom 3D printed supports. With this configuration, we selected 180 random poses within the robot working space to be reached in a fixed time of 20 seconds for a total duration of 1 hour. Additionally, each finger moved sequentially through its whole range of motion (from fully extended to fully closed) for the whole trial and the described procedure was repeated 5 times.

The data from the accelerometer, gyroscope and magnetometer in the 9-axis IMUs was integrated with a sensor fusion algorithm and the resulting values were used to measure the orientation of the finger joints. IMU sensors are also affected by drifting problems which are essentially caused by the integration of the error over time and by the fluctuations of the magnetic field [8] although the long duration of the experiment allowed us to observe this behaviour. The data from the sensors

¹<https://www.rethinkrobotics.com>

²<https://www.active8robots.com/ar10-robotic-hand>

Fig. 2. The plot shows the euclidian norm of the three axis of the euler angle representation over time. It can be noticed how the difference increases over time due to the drifting of the magnetometer. The Y-axis is expressed in degrees and the time in minutes.

Fig. 3. In the figure are represent the values obtained by concatenating the data from each trial. The three boxplots respectively show the spread of the values for the three euler angles in degrees. The blue star represents the mean while the yellow line is the median value.

were gathered from the socket connection and compared with the ROS Transform of the hand connected to Baxter.

IV. RESULTS

The experiment showed how the performance of the glove tend to drift over time with respect to the reference frame of the robot indicated by the ROS Transform (TF) package. In Figure 2 are shown the euclidian norm of the euler angles over time for the sensor positioned on the back of the hand. This value is represented in degrees and shows how the drifting gets worse over time.

We restricted the length of the data to 20 minutes in order to reduce the impact of this inaccuracy over time. This value was selected by averaging the signal durations that resulted

after a 7.5 degree threshold was applied and the remaining data was discarded.

The resulting sequences obtained from the previous step were concatenated and plotted by means of boxplots to show how the spread of the error. Figure 3 illustrates for each axis of the euler angle representation the corresponding boxplot with standard deviation mean and median value for the overall data of the 11 sensors.

V. CONCLUSION

In our paper we presented a low-cost IMU-based Data Glove with a modular design that allows to adjust the number of sensors according to the task. The functionality of this hardware can be further extended by adding different types of sensors such as pressure sensors or haptic feedback modules thanks to the I2C communication. We also showed the results from the tests we carried out on this device showing its performance in static and dynamic conditions and the drawbacks caused by the drifting of the IMU sensors.

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